

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Evaluation of rice germplasm in Bangkok

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We evaluated 198 local rices from the National Rice Seed Storage Laboratory for Genetic Resources for 36 agronomic traits. Culm number, panicle length, culm length, blade color, and grain yield varied considerably.

At Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, soil pH is around 4.7. Annual rainfall averages 109.58 mm; temperature averages 28 °C (33 °C maximum and 24 °C minimum).

The 1988-89 experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design.

Range, mean, and coefficient of variation for different characters in rice germplasm collection in Thailand.

Character	Range	Mean	SD	CV (%)
Leaf length (cm)	41.4 - 84.2	65.52	7.87	12.01
Leaf width (cm)	0.5 - 2.1	1.35	0.22	16.41
Culm length (cm)	60.0 - 167.8	133.80	20.00	14.95
Ligule length (cm)	6.4 - 25.0	17.78	5.55	31.24
Culm number	2 - 19	10.25	2.98	29.04
Panicle length (cm)	21.5 - 32.8	27.46	16.16	58.86
100-grain weight (g)	2.2 - 3.6	2.96	0.25	8.52

Plants were spaced 25 × 33 cm with four 5-m-long rows/plot. RD7, KDML, 105, and KTH17 were the standard checks.

Most of the varieties screened did not differ in morphology such as blade pubescence. Ligule was white with two clefts. Stigma was yellow. Apiculus was white in most rices, but red at the apex in Sao Nueng (GS.5699) and Niaw Nak (GS.5701).

Considerable variation in culm length and panicle length was observed among varieties (see table). Genotypes with desirable characters can be used as parents in breeding programs for specific locations.

Low SD for leaf width, leaf length, culm number, and 100-grain weight indicates limited scope for selection of these characters. ■

Findings from a 28-yr seed viability experiment

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In April 1963, Peter R. Jennings and I set up a germplasm bank seed storage experiment. Seed lots of varieties Siam 29, Peta, and Chianan 8 were dried at 50 °C in a convection oven to 13, 11, 7, 5, and 3.5% wet basis initial seed moisture content. After cooling, the seed lots were embedded in liberal amounts of silica gel inside airtight 1 1/2-gallon glass jars. The equilibrium seed moisture content was maintained at about 8.5%, and the jars kept at 2 °C.

Twice a year, 500 seeds of each variety were sprouted in petri dishes in 100-seed lots to measure viability. Seeds dried to 11% moisture content have shown the least drop in viability over 28 yr (see figure). This moisture content is the average of seeds kept in IRGC's short-term storage room.

The viability reading shows

Changes in seed viability over time of controlled varieties kept at 2 °C cold storeroom.

- two dormant varieties (Siam and Peta) began with moderately low germination (60-80%), which increased markedly after dormancy expired; viability remained around 96% to early 1991.
- viability of nondormant Chianan 8 deteriorated rapidly after 8 yr; by 1990, viability was less than 5%.

The longevity pattern between the indica varieties dominant in the tropics and the sinica varieties dominant in the subtropics is striking, and little known to rice workers and seed physiologists.

These findings led IRGC staff to set up a control set of 8-10 representative varieties from major rice-growing countries in the IRGC medium-term (2 °C, 40%